

A DOCTOR-PATIENT RELATIONSHIP IN HEALTHCARE DELIVERY AT PENTECOST HOSPITAL, LANKWANTANANG - MADINA, GREATER ACCRA REGION - GHANA.

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Abstract

This research topic was investigated by some groups of medical experts such as Israel journal of health policy research, open access Macedonian journal of medical sciences in Iran, British journal of general sciences and WHO. The views expressed by the aforementioned experts triggered the researcher to investigate the impact of good doctor-patient relationship in healthcare delivery in the aforesaid hospital to underscore the key nature of the human bond between the healthcare provider and the patient as a partnership, which is essential to the healing process.

Many forums have also expressed their views on the topic to depict a positive doctor patient relationship as a critical component of high-quality medical care. Perhaps the personal touch that is so important for healthy doctor patient connection has been diminished by the intense reliance on technology for diagnostic therapeutic procedures and the intense demands placed on the doctor's time. Numerous societal, economic, political, and health systems-related factors influence the doctor patient relationship.

This article discusses the impact of a good doctor patient relationship in healthcare delivery at Pentecost hospital. It further identifies factors hindering a good doctor patient relationship, the benefits, and talks about the improvement in order to enhance healthcare delivery.

A cross-sectional study design with both qualitative and quantitative method was employed for the purpose of the study to understand the impact of doctor-patient relationship in healthcare delivery.

A probability sample size of 50 respondents mainly, patients who have undergone their appointment with the doctor were engaged in focus group discussions and observations. Tables, graphs and charts were used in the explanations for clear understanding. Frequencies and percentages were also used as statistical tools to present the results of the study.

Generally, the majority of the respondents had a positive treatment outcome, good interaction with the doctors even though a few complained that the gender of the doctor, their socioeconomic and educational status and age got in the way of connecting well and understanding the doctor and also in decision making.

The researchers therefore concluded that when there is a good doctor-patient relationship, it will result in overall benefits for both the health organization and patients.

They also made recommendation of increasing knowledge and awareness of doctor-patient

relationship in healthcare services delivery. Both health workers and patients should be briefed on the importance and benefits of having a good interpersonal relationship among themselves and how it affects service delivery in the health facility.

Keywords: Doctor, Patient, Doctor patient relationship (DPR) and healthcare delivery.

1. Introduction

A doctor-patient relationship (DPR) is considered to be a core element in ethical principles of medicine thus, it is a central part of healthcare and the practice of medicine. A doctor is a health professional who practices medicine and is concerned in promoting, maintaining or restoring the health of individuals. Patient is a person receiving or registered to receive medical treatment. Communication plays a vital role when it comes to the provision of healthcare services, and a physician communication style is crucial to the quality and the strength of the doctor-patient relationship. Research shows that most patients when visiting the hospital for medical treatment find it really difficult to open up easily in revealing their private health conditions to doctors hence making the work of both the healthcare providers and organization very difficult.

As a doctor it is your responsibility to build a relationship of trust, respect, communication and understanding among your patients. These four (4) key elements in building a mutual relationship helps the patient gain confidence in the competence of their physician making it easy to confide in them (Renter,2015).

A poor doctor-patient relationship compromises the physician's inability to make a full assessment on the patient's diagnosis and proposed treatment. Therefore, this study will answer the following research questions:

- What are the factors hindering a good doctor-patient relationship in healthcare?
- What are the benefits and effects of a good doctor-patient relationship to the health facility?
- How do we improve the doctor-patient relationship to enhance healthcare delivery?

2. Literature Review

2.1 The Development of doctor-patient bond

Over the years, the doctor-patient relationship has undergone changes. Before the last 20 years, the connection was mostly one of a patient asking for assistance and a doctor, with the patient silently contributing to the decisions. In the paternalistic approach, the physician uses his training to select the necessary procedures and therapies that have the best chance of regaining the patient's health. Every piece of information provided to the patient is chosen to entice them to accept the recommendations made by the doctor. Over the past 20 years, there have been challenges to Parsons T. The social system (Free Press, New York, 1951), which describes the asymmetrical or imbalanced connection between a doctor and patient. Critics have suggested that patients should play a more active, independent, and patient-centered role in advocating for increased patient autonomy, less physician dominance, and increased mutual participation. This patient-focused position.

(Kaba et al, February, 2007) The interaction between a doctor and patient has two dimensions:

- The instrumental component pertains to the physician's proficiency in carrying out the technical facets of healthcare, including administering prescription drugs, conducting physical examinations, and conducting diagnostic testing.
- The expressive elements, such as the doctor's approach to the patient and the affective aspects of the relationship, such as warmth and empathy, represent the art of medicine.

2.2 The Four Models of a Doctor-Patient Relationship

(Emanuel et al, 1992) In 1992, Linda Emanuel and Ezekiel Emanuel created four models of a doctor-patient relationship. These models are as follows:

- The Active-Passive Model, also known as the Paternalistic Model, is predicated on doctors treating their patients like inanimate objects. In an emergency situation where the patient might be unconscious or where a treatment delay could result in permanent damage, this model may be appropriate.
- The Interpretive Model (Guidance-Cooperation Model) places a doctor in a position of power because they possess knowledge that the patient does not. In the best interest of the patient, the doctor is supposed to make decisions and offer advice. It is expected of the patient to follow their decision.
- The Mutual Participation Model (Informative Model) The doctor and patient are partners on an equal footing. Since the patient is considered an expert in their own life experiences and objectives, their involvement is crucial in the treatment plan. According to this model, both parties must be equally powerful, reliant on one another, and involved in activities that they find equally fulfilling.
- The Deliberative Model, which is like having a teacher or friend by your side, enables the doctor to discuss the best course of action with you.

2.2 Fig 1 (Emanuel et al, 1992) Comparing the four models

	Informative	Interpretive	Deliberative	Paternalistic
Patient values	Define, fixed and known to the patient	Inchoate and conflicting, requiring elucidation	Open to development and revision through moral discussion.	Objective and shared by physician and patient
Physicians obligations	Providing relevant ,factual information and implementing patient's	Elucidating and interpreting relevant patient values as well as informing and implementing	Persuading the patient of the most admirable values as informing and implementing	Promoting the patient's well-being independent of the patient's

	selected intervention	the patient's selected intervention	the patient's selected intervention	current preferences.
Concept of patient autonomy	Choice of, and control over, medical care	Self-understanding relevant to medical care	Moral self-development relevant to medical care	Assenting to objective values
Conception of physician's role	Competent technical expert	Counselor or advisor	Friend or teacher	Guardian

2.3 Proficiency in medical-patient dialogue

Effective doctor-patient communication is a critical clinical function in establishing a therapeutic doctor-patient relationship, which is medicine's heart and soul. This is critical in providing high-quality health care. Many patients complain and become unhappy from a breakdown in the doctor-patient relationship. Many doctors, on the other hand, tend to exaggerate their communication skills. Much has been written about this crucial topic in the literature over the years.

A doctor's communication and interpersonal skills include the ability to gather data for the purpose of providing an accurate diagnosis, offering appropriate counseling, providing therapeutic instructions, and fostering compassionate relationships with patients. (Henderson et al, 2002). These are critical clinical competencies for the efficient provision of medical care with the ultimate objective of achieving the best possible result and patient satisfaction. A therapeutic doctor-patient relationship requires more than just basic communication skills to be established and maintained. This relationship involves shared views and feelings regarding the nature of the problem, treatment objectives, and psychological support. Interpersonal skills are the foundation upon which this basic communication ability is built. Physician-centered and patient-centered strategies are combined in appropriate communication. The ultimate goal of any doctor-patient interaction should be to enhance the patient's health and level of care. Studies on doctor-patient communication showed patient dissatisfaction, despite the fact that many doctors felt the communication was excellent or even great. (A. Brèdet al., 2005). Physicians often overstate their communication abilities. Tongue et al. report that while 75% of orthopedic surgeons think they communicate with their patients satisfactorily, only 21% of patients think their doctors do so successfully. In surveys, patients have often expressed a wish for better communication with their physicians. The ancient Greek Cos school of medicine is where patient-centered medicine first emerged. Contrarily, patient-centered medicine has not always been the standard. For example, because there were few options for cancer treatment in the 1950s and 1970s, the majority of doctors thought it was cruel and detrimental to their patients' health to break bad news to them. In recent years, the medical model has changed from paternalism to individualism. (F. D. Duffy and others, 2004). The shared decision paradigm that exists today is a result of the health consumer movement. The three major goals of current doctor-patient communication are to establish a positive interpersonal relationship, facilitate information interchange, and include patients in decision-making. Doctors' "bedside manner," which

patients rate as a primary predictor of their doctors' overall competency, determines effective doctor-patient communication.

Good doctor-patient communication has the ability to help patients regulate their emotions, understand medical information more easily, and better identify their needs, perceptions, and expectations. Patients who report strong communication with their doctor are more likely to be satisfied with their care, especially when it comes to sharing relevant information for an accurate diagnosis of their problems, following recommendations, and sticking to the prescribed therapy. Patients' satisfaction with the nature of their treatment and the need for follow-up is closely linked to their recovery. (Longnecker et al, 2010).

Patient and doctor satisfaction improves when the encounter is more patient-centered. Patients who are satisfied are less likely to file official complaints or launch malpractice investigations. Doctors benefit from satisfied patients because they have more job satisfaction, less work-related stress, and less burnout. (Hall J. A. et al, 1981).

Effective physician patient communication has been shown to positively influence health outcomes by increasing patient satisfaction, leading to greater patient understanding of health problems and treatments available, contributing to better adherence to treatment plans, and providing support and reassurance to patients. Building a good doctor-patient relationship begins with effective doctor-patient communication. Quality care requires safe methods and good, patient-centered communication. Good doctor-patient communication has the ability to help patients regulate their emotions, understand medical information more easily, and better identify their needs, perceptions, and expectations. Doctors with superior communication and interpersonal skills can spot problems sooner, avoid medical emergencies and costly interventions, and provide better support to their patients. According to recent studies, one of the top causes of medical errors and patient harm is inadequate communication among healthcare providers. Patients' anxiety and terror, doctors' workload, fear of litigation, or verbal abuse, unrealistic patient expectations and fear of physical harm are all hurdles to good communication in the doctor-patient relationship. (Roter et al, 1981).

2.4 How to build a good relationship with your patient?

(Mills, 2020) A good rapport with patients leads to a tight and pleasant relationship. It enables you to comprehend your patient's emotions and effectively communicate with them.

In nursing, the value of rapport cannot be overstated. It allows you to connect with your patients and can help you provide better treatment. As a result, nurses must look for ways to establish rapport with each patient. Rapport, on the other hand, is not a "one-size-fits-all" instrument. Using the patient's communication preferences and current health state, you can establish rapport.

There is no class on how to create rapport with patients, unfortunately. Rapport is a skill that takes time to master. It could also be easier for some patients than others. Even if the nurse-patient interaction is short, you should try to create rapport.

7 ways to build a relationship with your patient.

1. Make direct eye contact

Keeping eye contact conveys concern and sympathy. It can also demonstrate concern and empathy for your patient's condition. Eye contact and social touch communicate understanding and link you to your patients.

2. Demonstrate Empathy

Empathy is the ability to grasp the circumstance, perspective, and feelings of the patient. It enables you to provide more tailored patient care. The compassionate nurse expresses and acts on their knowledge of the patient.

3. Transparency in Communication

According to one study, effective communication is a critical element in improving patient outcomes. It will be easier to create rapport if you understand your patient's communication preferences and mental condition. One method to do this is to inform your patient of new instructions or changes in their health. Encouraging your patient to tell you about their feelings is another. One of the most important nurse communication skills for success is open communication.

4. Personalize it

Being a patient can be frightening. Take the time to get to know your patients to make their stay more comfortable. Inquire about their friends and family, as well as their hobbies and other significant areas of their lives. This shows that you want to know them as a person, not just as a patient. This is a simple method for learning how to establish rapport with your patients.

5. Listening actively

Active listening is an important component of holistic healing. It is a non-intrusive method of sharing a patient's feelings and thoughts. Follow these steps to practice active listening: - Pay attention to what the patient is saying.

- Tell the patient what you just heard.

- Double-check your reflection with the patient to make sure it's accurate.

Active listening aims to reflect the emotion or intent underlying someone's words. It would be beneficial if you listened to comprehend rather than respond. One of numerous strategies to create rapport is to practice active listening.

6. Mirroring exercises

Rapport is easily established by matching the patient's demeanor, mood, and cadence. To develop a synchronous link, you may even need to raise your voice to match a loud patient. Then, with a low voice and deliberate gestures, guide the patient to a more suitable location. During challenging interactions, use mirroring to become connected to the patient.

7. Keep your word.

One of the most effective methods to create connection with patients is to keep your word. If you say you'll do something, follow through. Communicate with the patient if your ability to finish a task changes. Don't make promises you can't keep. Keeping your word with patients fosters not simply rapport, but also trust.

2.5 Relationship aspects (Browning, 2018)

1. Informed Consent

The standard medical practice for treating patients and their families with respect is for the doctor to be honest in informing them about their condition and to be forthright in asking for their consent before

administering therapy. In many cultures, there has been a trend away from paternalism, or the belief that "the doctor always knows best," to the idea that patients should have a say in how their care is delivered and the right to grant informed consent to medical operations. Informed consent can be difficult to handle in a doctor–patient relationship, especially when patients do not want to hear the reality about their illness. Additionally, there are ethical considerations about the use of placebos. Is it true that administering a sugar tablet undermines the doctor-patient relationship? Is it possible to have a respectful and consent-based doctor–patient relationship while deceiving a patient for his or her own good? These types of questions arise frequently in the healthcare system, and the solutions to all of them are typically ambiguous, but they should be guided by medical ethics.

2. Making decisions

Both the doctor and the patient are involved in treatment decisions in shared decision-making. There are many different definitions of what shared decision making entails, but the most frequent one involves both sides sharing information, taking measures to develop consensus, and reaching a treatment agreement. The doctor does not tell the patient what to do; instead, the patient's autonomy is respected, and they get to pick the medical treatment they desire. A practice that is an alternative to this is for a doctor to make a person's health decisions without taking into account that person's treatment goals or allowing that person's input into the decision-making process. This is unethical and goes against the concept of personal autonomy and freedom. Ulrich Beck's *World at Risk* covers the entire spectrum of a physician's involvement of a patient in treatment decisions. Beck's Negotiated Approach to risk communication is at one end of the spectrum, in which the communicator maintains an open dialogue with the patient and comes to an agreement that is acceptable to both the patient and the physician. The majority of doctors use some form of this communication model, as it is only through this strategy that a doctor can preserve his or her patient's open collaboration. The Technocratic Approach to risk communication is on the other end of the spectrum, in which the physician exerts authoritarian control over the patient's treatment and forces the patient to accept the treatment plan with which they are presented in a paternalistic manner. This communication model elevates the physician to omniscience and omnipotence over the patient, leaving little room for patient input into treatment decisions.

3. Communication style of doctors

The quality and strength of the doctor–patient connection are dependent on physician communication style. Patient-centered communication has been demonstrated to improve the doctor–patient relationship through asking open-ended questions, maintaining a friendly demeanor, fostering emotional expression, and displaying interest in the patient's life. This form of communication has also been demonstrated to reduce other unfavorable attitudes or beliefs that patients may have about doctors or healthcare in general, as well as enhance treatment compliance. Self-disclosure by the physician, in particular, is another form of communication that benefits the patient-provider relationship. Historically, medical schools have discouraged physicians from providing personal or emotional information to patients, citing the importance of neutrality and professionalism. Self-disclosure by doctors, on the other hand, has been demonstrated to improve rapport, patient trust, their willingness to provide information, and the patient's desire to continue seeing the doctor. These impacts were linked to empathy, which is another key characteristic that is sometimes overlooked in physician education. A physician's reaction to a patient's emotional expression can influence the quality

of the connection and how comfortable patients are discussing delicate concerns, feelings, or information that is crucial to their diagnosis or care. Patients have been demonstrated to benefit from more passive, neutral response styles that allow them to elaborate on their sentiments and help them feel more at ease. Avoidance or dismissal of a patient's emotional expression by a physician may deter the patient from sharing their feelings and harm their relationship with their provider.

4. Superiority of physicians.

Due to the inherent power dynamic of the physician's control over the patient's health, a physician has traditionally been perceived as dominant or superior to the patient in the paternalistic model. In this concept, doctors would only provide the patient the facts they needed to convince them of their treatment plan. The physician–patient relationship is further complicated by the patient's suffering (patient comes from the Latin *patior*, which means "to suffer") and limited ability to relieve it without the physician's assistance, which can lead to desperation and reliance on the physician. A physician should be aware of these differences in order to create a welcoming, trusting environment and improve patient communication. Additionally, creating a shared care practice with a stronger emphasis on patient empowerment and accepting greater responsibility for their own care may be good to the doctor–patient relationship. Patients who seek medical advice frequently do not comprehend or are unaware of the medical science behind their disease, which is why they seek medical advice in the first place. Without their doctor's explanation, a patient with no medical or scientific experience may not be able to understand what is going on with their body. As a result, for the patient, this can be a frightening and frustrating experience, filled with a sense of powerlessness and uncertainty. However, in rare cases, this pattern is not followed, and patients are forced to learn about their conditions due to a lack of expertise.

An in-depth discussion of the diagnosis, lab results, treatment options, and outcomes in layman's words can be encouraging and offer the patient a sense of control over their illness. At the same time, excellent communication between a doctor and their patient can help to build the physician–patient relationship while also promoting greater treatment adherence and health outcomes.

5. Coercion

Under certain circumstances, healthcare staff can involuntarily treat patients, imprison them, or administer drugs to change their ability to think. They may also use "informal coercion," in which they use information or access to social services to manipulate a patient.

6. Deception

In the doctor–patient relationship, lying is very common. After medical blunders, doctors only give patients the most basic facts. Patients may tell doctors lies to avoid taking responsibility for unsatisfactory outcomes. Doctors claim that they avoid providing information to patients because they believe it may confuse them, inflict agony, or destroy their hope. They may lie to avoid having to talk about incapacity or death, or to promote a specific treatment option. The experience of being deceived can cause a person to lose faith in herself or others. It may cause people to lose trust in their church, community, or society. To avoid being hurt, people may become avoidant. Patients may seek monetary and legal redress.

Patients may lie to doctors for financial motives, such as receiving disability compensation, drug access, or avoiding incarceration. Patients may lie out of shame or humiliation. Palmeira and Sterne propose that healthcare personnel acknowledge patients' reasons to lie in order to look in a positive light in

order to prevent patient deception. Obtaining truth as an ongoing process to promote truthfulness in doctor–patient relationships, they recommend discussions regarding the amount of information and depth parties wish to convey. They provide many psychological frameworks and motivations for lying: according to attachment theory, lying may be employed to avoid disclosing facts about an individual and therefore the risk of rejection or shame, or to exaggerate in order to get protection or care. They also discuss the idea of protecting and maintaining their ego ideals.

2.6 Factors hindering good DPR.

- Doctors see patients from many ethnic backgrounds as a result of migration. Communication is hampered as a result of this. It's crucial to understand which barriers and facilitators influence the quality of intercultural communication (ICC) before developing training programs for clinicians. Working with people from other cultures will become increasingly important as national economies evolve, overlap, and combine. Intercultural communication entails the exchange of information among people from other cultures and social groupings, including those from various religious, social, ethnic, and educational backgrounds. It aims to comprehend the differences in how people from other cultures behave, communicate, and see the world. (John Sinden, 2021). Intercultural communication hinders a good-doctor patient relationship.
- Patients who choose faith over medicine postpone critical medical care, refuse life-saving surgeries, and stop taking necessary medications because of their religious convictions. Health care providers must learn to appreciate and not be insulted or rejected when patients make decisions based on their religious views.
- Low-income people and those without health insurance have poorer communication satisfaction and have less access to healthcare. Depending on the patient's socioeconomic class, changes in physician communication behavior exist. Hence, a patient's socioeconomic affects a good doctor-patient relationship.
- An individual level of education hinders a good doctor-patient relationship. An individual who is not really inclined when it comes to school knowledge finds it difficult to interact and understand his or her physicians. And also aged individuals find it difficult to interact and understand the diagnosis and treatment plan given to them.
- Gender thus being a male or female is a factor of a good-patient relationship. The gender of the doctor and the patient has an impact on the likelihood of a psychosocial communication pattern, especially when female general practitioners communicate with female patients or a male practitioner speaks to the male. Patients spoke to female physicians more than male physicians, disclosed more biological and psychosocial information, and made more positive statements to female physicians, according to the study. Female physicians were more forceful, and patients were more likely to interrupt them.
- Age is relevant to both patient satisfaction and doctor interaction. Research shows that the aged have the maximum satisfaction in terms of healthcare than the youth. This is because most doctors interact friendly and explain to them more regarding issues about their health. But for the youth it's vice versa.
- Altered mental state

- Illness
- Inability to speak to them or have a face to face discussion with the doctor.
- Time constraints on physician or patient.
- Medication effects
- Dysphonia
- Psychological or emotional distress.

Solutions to the factors hindering a good doctor patient relationship.

- Every patient should be treated equally irrespective of their cultural background, religion, level of education, gender, age and socioeconomic status.
- Doctors and health workers shouldn't be biased when delivering healthcare services.
- Doctors should help explain the treatment plans and diagnosis administered to the patient and they should be friendly to their patient.

2.7 Situation that might bring an end to Doctor-patient bond

(Herndon et al, 2002) The doctor-patient connection necessitates both vulnerability and trust. It is one of the most powerful and important moments that humans have shared. This relationship and the encounters that result from it, however, are not always perfect. Patients may communicate secrets, concerns, and fears to doctors that they have not yet revealed to friends or family members. Trusting a doctor allows them to preserve or restore their health and well-being.

Some situations might bring about a physician's discharge of patients and ending of DPR.

The doctor-patient relationship may terminate if the patient:

- The doctor determines the patient requires care from other specialists
- The patient constantly misses appointments
- The doctor refuses treatment because of the patient's nationality, religion, or other reasons
- The patient is neglected from prompt professional care without an agreement to continue such care (patient abandonment).

2.8 Means for improvement

1. Communication Skills

Both style and content are important in communication. Skillful communication includes things like active listening, empathy, and the use of open-ended inquiries. Improved doctor-patient communication has been shown to promote patient involvement and adherence to suggested therapy, as well as influence patient satisfaction, adherence, and health-care utilization, as well as improve care quality and results. In the practice of medicine, breaking bad news to patients is a complex and difficult communication undertaking. When it comes to giving bad news, creating relationships is very vital. Understanding patients' viewpoints, communicating information, and patients' knowledge and expectations are all important considerations. Miscommunication can have major consequences, as it can impair patients' understanding, treatment expectations, and participation in treatment planning.

Miscommunication also lowers patient satisfaction with medical care, as well as their sense of hopefulness and subsequent psychological adjustment. (Hall et al, 1981).

2. Training

Doctors are not born with exceptional communication skills because they possess a variety of natural abilities. Instead, if there is adequate motivation and incentive for self-awareness, self-monitoring, and training, individuals can understand the theory of excellent doctor-patient communication, learn and practice these skills, and be capable of improving their communication style. Doctor-patient communication has been found to improve with communication skills training. The enhanced habits, however, may fade over time. As a result, it is critical to practice new skills and receive regular feedback on the acquired behavior. Some argue that medical education should go beyond skill training to enhance clinicians' attention to the unique experiences of their patients. (Stewart M. et al, 2000).

3. Cooperation in Communication

Cooperation in communication is a two-way information sharing relationship that is reciprocal and dynamic. Doctors should, in an ideal world, cooperate with their patients to offer the best care possible, because doctors' decisions are often based on fast, biased assessments. This necessitates clinicians taking time or creating chances to provide and discuss treatment options with patients, as well as sharing responsibility and control. To allow for collaborative decision making, successful information exchange ensures that concerns are elicited and investigated, as well as that explanations of treatment alternatives are balanced and understood. Rather than a standardized protocol, the doctor facilitates discussion and negotiation with patients, and treatment options are evaluated and tailored to the context of the patients' situation and needs. To maximize adherence and ensure the best outcome, care options must be developed collaboratively between doctor and patient, taking into account patient expectations, outcome preferences, level of risk acceptance, and any associated costs. (DiMatteo M. R, 1998).

4. Conflict Management

In pediatric palliative care, Feudtner documented circumstances in which the source of disagreements was frequently not stated. The root cause was frequently unstated and so obscure or unknown to one or both parties, resulting in emotions of discontent. Conflict is frequently a difficult circumstance because it might elicit feelings of helplessness, irritation, bewilderment, rage, uncertainty, failure, or despair. To de-escalate the situation and turn relationship problems into clinical successes, the doctor should recognize these feelings and build abilities to identify harmful responses in the patient or oneself. Aside from decreasing avoidance behavior, which stops patients from expressing their ideas, successful doctor-patient communication should include meaningful discourse, which includes comprehension of both parties' perspectives by transitioning from a perspective that is steadfast in one's belief to a more inquisitive approach that seeks to examine the subject from a different angle. Recognizing the influence of patient reciprocation of communication and affect in a medical visit is critical because it may aid in the creation of good exchanges to defuse harmful patterns.

2.9 How to manage a difficult doctor-patient relationship?

A tense doctor-patient relationship can have serious implications for both the doctor and the patient. Difficult relationships can lead to medical care that is frustrating, dissatisfying, combative, and costly. A

breakdown in communication between the physician and the patient is frequently the cause of a tense relationship. Technical communication hurdles, difficulties discussing certain issues, unmet or violated norms and expectations (both physician and patient), and a personality mismatch between the physician and the patient are some of the specific factors.

Keeping professional self-esteem, maintaining physician-patient continuity, minimizing "medicalization" of the problem by limiting the use of tests and procedures, and minimizing hospitalization and referral are all management goals for the challenging relationship. It's also crucial to realize that, even if the relationship is still stressful or difficult, it can be effectively managed with appropriate strategies. (T L Schwenk et al,1992).

2.10 The importance of relationship-building in patient retention.

(Google Scholar, 2019) Doctors and other healthcare professionals recognize the need of developing a positive rapport with patients in order to offer outstanding medical care. A strong patient-provider relationship promotes collaboration and allows for more learning about a patient's specific health needs. This allows clinicians to better connect patients with therapies and resources that will help them improve their overall health. Building and maintaining solid relationships at the corporate level is now more crucial than ever. Consider this: premiums, deductibles, and copays are all increasing for modern healthcare customers. As a result, they've taken it upon themselves to ensure that the healthcare systems they utilize are the most cost-effective. Consumers are looking for healthcare organizations that balance price and value by looking at competitive pricing, overall care quality, and customer service. Given that it costs five times more to acquire a new customer than it does to keep an existing one, corporations are increasingly focusing on patient retention. Organizations can find opportunities to deliver better value across the patient's healthcare experience by creating relationships with patients across the healthcare system, helping to generate patients for life. Given that it costs five times more to acquire a new customer than it does to keep an existing one, corporations are increasingly focusing on patient retention. Organizations can find opportunities to deliver better value across the patient's healthcare experience by creating relationships with patients across the healthcare system, helping to generate patients for life. In light of this, we'll look at four reasons why relationship management is so important for patient retention.

1. Strong relationships boost patients' confidence.

The "single most significant hallmark of great care," according to the 2017 Consumer Health Care Priorities research, What Patients and Doctors Want from the Health Care System, was the patient-provider interaction. Patients want to know that their healthcare practitioner has taken the time to learn about their specific needs and is prepared to give the quality of care they anticipate. Patients want the same high-quality relationship with their doctors across departments, staff, and marketing initiatives in a healthcare firm. Patients also want customization from such connections, demonstrating that an organization has taken the time to understand their unique healthcare needs. After all, people expect their interactions with other brands, not only healthcare, to go the same way. Healthcare firms may meet these patient demands by using CRM to combine fragmented patient data and create personalized engagements tailored to the individual's unique healthcare journey. Patient connections can be created

and maintained this way, leading to increased patient trust in the organization's ability to understand and cater to their healthcare requirements. (Fallon et al, 2015).

2. Relationships assist patients in becoming more involved in their own care.

Consumers nowadays appreciate being included in discussions about their healthcare treatment options. They also want to be connected to the information and assistance that will help them understand their unique healthcare needs and make better health and wellness decisions. When companies make an effort to build relationships with their customers, they reap two rewards: First, they can gain a better understanding of each patient's unique medical history and healthcare needs. This gives the organization the information it needs to link a patient to the tools and resources they need to learn about their needs and treatment options while also allowing them to make the decisions they want to make.

Second, partnerships expand the amount of chances for an organization to include a patient in their healthcare decision-making process. The better an organization understands a patient, the better it can match the patient with specific resources, treatment options, and information.

Furthermore, the better the patient-organization relationship, the more likely these personalized resources and information will resonate and boost retention efforts.

3. Strong relationships lead to customers' best experiences.

Patients who consistently feel connected to their healthcare organization on a personal level are more likely to have positive overall experiences across the healthcare continuum. With this in mind, stronger patient relationships demonstrate value that goes above and beyond quality treatment and care. The greater value a healthcare organization can provide, the more they will differentiate from competing healthcare organizations. It's also worth mentioning that in today's value-based care model, any hint of a bad overall experience for patients might hurt customer acquisition and retention efforts.

Organizations can better anticipate patient requirements and provide proactive treatment by creating and cultivating strong long-term patient relationships, which leads to improved health outcomes and a better overall customer experience. Furthermore, companies with stronger customer experience metrics produce far more revenue than they spend. Although better patient experience scores are often associated with greater per-patient expenses, research reveals that investments in patient experience not only raise costs, but also improve revenue.

4. Relationships help marketers optimize their efforts.

(McKinsey, 2023) Healthcare marketing efforts are more complicated, requiring a greater range of touchpoints and platforms to engage customers and keep existing patients throughout their healthcare journeys. Marketers must provide targeted, consistent, and personalized interactions across all of their marketing initiatives to effectively optimize campaigns. Marketers can construct 360-degree patient profiles that contain each patient's unique health journeys and allow marketers to personalize efforts to each individual patient's requirements and interests by exploiting patient data fed into the healthcare CRM. However, marketers will need more data on individual patients to feed into the HCRM in order to generate modern patient profiles. The patient relationship begins. Patients are more likely to interact with marketing efforts when there are stronger relationships across the healthcare organization; the more engagements a campaign can produce; the more analytics marketers can use to maximize the impact of future campaigns. Simply said, strengthening patient relationships is an investment in better healthcare marketing. Patients will want to interact with the healthcare organization more often if they

feel comfortable and confident that the organization understands them and is working to provide them with the best health and wellness solutions. This will increase the overall patient lifetime value. As a result, marketers will have more access to individual patient data, which will lead to better marketing campaign efforts down the road.

2.11 Patient behavior

(Dr. Maria Alice, 2018) The doctor–patient relationship is influenced by the patient's behavior. Patients' or their family members' rude or hostile behavior can also distract healthcare personnel, causing them to be less effective or make mistakes during a medical procedure. Medical personnel are under pressure to accomplish their jobs efficiently when dealing with issues in every healthcare setting. While a variety of things might influence how their job is completed, unfriendly patients and unappealing attitudes can have a significant impact. This is supported by studies conducted by Dr. Pete Hamburger, associate dean for research at Tel Aviv University. His research found that impolite and harsh attitudes toward medical personnel harmed their capacity to do some of their more routine and procedural activities. This is significant because if medical personnel fail to perform adequately in what should be easy activities, their capacity to operate successfully in critical situations will be harmed as well. While it is totally understood that patients are going through a difficult period, which is made much more difficult by stress from other external and internal sources, doctors and medical staff must be mindful of any harsh attitudes that may be directed their way.

2.12 Strengthening doctor-patient relationship.

(WHO, 2013) doctor-patient relationship is a critical factor in providing high-quality health care. People used to think of doctors as family members until recently, and their faith in them stretched far beyond the family's medical needs. However, anecdotal evidence suggests that the relationship between doctors and patients is deteriorating. This could be due to a variety of factors. One of the most significant factors is the commercialization and specialization of medicine, which places an excessive reliance on technology at the expense of meaningful human interaction between health-care seekers and providers. The significant reliance on technology for diagnostic and therapeutic treatments, as well as the doctor's time constraints, may have diluted the personal touch that is so important for a positive doctor-patient connection. A variety of societal, economic, political, and health-system-related elements also influence the doctor-patient interaction.

2.13 Positive effects of doctor-patient relationship on healthcare service delivery.

Increased access to care, greater patient knowledge and shared understanding, higher quality medical decisions, enhanced therapeutic alliances, increased social support, patient agency and empowerment, and better management of emotions are the positive effects of DPR.

2.14 The impact of a doctor-patient relationship on the future of healthcare.

(Fallon et al, 2015) Effective physician-patient communication has been shown to improve health outcomes by increasing patient satisfaction, increasing patient understanding of health problems and available treatments, promoting better adherence to treatment plans, and providing patients with

support and reassurance. Physicians and patients can collaborate to reach a common health goal through collaborative decision making. Trust is a vital component that influences communication between both sides in all aspects of the physician-patient relationship. The physician-patient connection will have a substantial impact on health outcomes as health care becomes more individualized and patient-centered.

The personalized health care model encourages clinicians and patients to collaborate in order to develop shared health objectives and a health plan to address recognized issues. Health care professionals will be able to address some of the hurdles to the adoption of more individualized approaches to health care in the future by better understanding the elements that drive patient-physician relationships. (Eustice, 2020).

3.0 Research Methodology

A cross-sectional study design with both qualitative and quantitative method was employed for the purpose of the study to understand the impact of doctor-patient relationship in healthcare delivery. Quantitative approach, according to Cresswell (2014) explains that the quantitative approach involves a formal, objective and systematic process of obtaining information about the world. Thus, it aims to test relationships, describe and examine cause and effect relations (Cresswell, 2014). Therefore, researchers who engage in quantitative research tend to employ large and random samples, test hypotheses, work deductively and generalize their findings to a wider population (Bergman, 2011). On the contrary, researchers utilizing qualitative approaches employ small samples, are non-reductionist about their subject matter and concern themselves with subjective experiences while studying the phenomenon in their natural setting (Bergman, 2011). My sample size was 50 respondents mainly, patients who have undergone their appointment with the doctor. This study employed a probability sampling technique which is a simple random sampling method. For the qualitative analysis, focus group discussions and observations were made. The analyses involved the use of tables, graphs and charts. The data for this study were presented with brief explanations for clear understanding. Frequencies and percentages were used as statistical tools to present the results of the study.

4.0 Discussions

The main findings of the study are as follows:

The age distribution from the survey indicates that the majority of the respondents in the sample fell within the 18 - 29 age bracket. Moreover, the ages of the respondents interviewed reflect a high rate of the population who are able to decide on what medical intervention they prefer.

Also, the result indicates that the majority of the respondents interviewed are educated and have both tertiary, senior high and junior high certificates which most probably indicates that they do have a fair knowledge of their health conditions and would be able to express themselves about whatever is happening to them.

Also, it was a clear indication that most of the participants, thus majority of the respondents were Christians while minority of the respondents were either Muslims or Traditionalist. One vital issue for discussion is the religious background of respondents. However, this was not left out as it is seen as an important aspect of this research. Religious values of individuals affect the doctor's clinical practice thus, causing patients to forgo needed medical care, refuse life-saving procedures and stop necessary medication, choosing faith instead of medicine. The results clearly indicate that, minority of the respondents had their religious value as a barrier in accepting the diagnosis/treatment plan of the doctor, while the other minority had trust issues, shyness, stress, depression (inability to express themselves and have a face to face interaction and emotional distress) as a barrier. But the majority had nothing getting in their way for a good doctor-patient relationship.

Generally, the majority of the respondents had a positive treatment outcome, good interaction with the doctors even though a few complained that the gender of the doctor, their socioeconomic and educational status and age got in the way of connecting well and understanding the doctor and also in decision making.

For the management and improvement aspect, the majority of the respondents stated that the waiting time should be worked on and a minority of the respondents also stated that making appointments, politeness of other health workers and easy access to care at other departmental units should be managed and worked on.

Lastly, for the focus group discussion and observations, most patients did have a positive outcome and maximum satisfaction to the health services rendered. A few had stress, depression, shyness, religious values and trust issues getting in their way but it was well managed and handled well by most doctors/physicians they visited. Majority in the focus group discussions also stated that the waiting time should be worked on and minority of the respondents also stated that making appointments, politeness of other health workers and easy access to care at other departmental units should be managed and worked on.

5.0 Conclusion

The researchers have found out from the study that doctor patient relationship affects the performance of the health facility and that it is critical to educate both doctors and patients about having a good doctor patient relationship which leads to more frequent, freely given quality information regarding the patient's ailment and, as a result, better healthcare for the patient and their family and to improve both the accuracy of the diagnosis and the patient's awareness of the ailment.

The researchers therefore concluded that when there is a good doctor-patient relationship, it will result in overall benefits for both the health organization and patients.

6.0 Recommendation

The following recommendations are made for considerations for a good doctor-patient relationship in health service delivery:

- There should be increasing knowledge and awareness of doctor-patient relationship in healthcare services delivery. Both health workers and patients should be briefed on the importance and

benefits of having a good interpersonal relationship among themselves and how it affects service delivery in the health facility.

- Health workers should demonstrate sympathy and empathy. They shouldn't portray behaviors which are offensive and rude to the patients. For example: for the doctors, if delivering a bad news, show your patient that you understand his or her concerns and can appreciate how they are feeling. If you have a personal experience that relates to their situation, share your story. It can help them feel more connected to you and view you as not only a doctor but as a person.
- Focus on the positive, not just the negative. Some conditions can be treated with an antibiotic or analgesic, but others require substantial lifestyle changes. Patients will likely resist major alterations to their day-to-day routine, especially if it's something they've been doing for years. For example: smoking or unhealthy eating habits. Rather than focusing only on the negative consequences of maintaining their current lifestyle, concentrate on the benefits of these changes and how they can improve the patient's quality of life.
- Practice Shared Decision Making. It is a collaborative approach to healthcare where physicians and patients work together to develop the best treatment plan. Instead of the provider making all the care decisions on behalf of the patient, the patient is involved in discussions about various treatment options, reviews, the pros and cons of each and then decides how they would like to proceed.
- Recognize cultural differences. While some behaviors are perfectly acceptable in one culture, they could be considered extremely rude in another. Physicians must recognize that each culture has its own distinct customs and adjust the way they interact with patients based on these norms. Physicians who consider a patient's unique culture, values and beliefs during interactions will be able to build better rapport, making their patients feel appreciated and respected.
- The waiting time and the hospital's bad network system should be worked on. The health facility should have a good ISP (Internet Service Provider) which would provide a good internet service for the health facility for their electronic health record (EHRs). Doing this would help reduce the waiting time for most patients and improve upon the services of the health facility.

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